

Impact and Relevance of Adopt-a-School Program Among Public Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the impact and relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) among public schools within the Manapla District of the Division of Negros Occidental for the school year 2025–2026, serving as a foundation for school-based policy formulation. Utilizing a mixed-method sequential explanatory design, the study employed document analysis, observations, and structured interviews to gather data from the respondents consisted of 207 teachers, 14 school leaders, and 128 PTA officers, for a total of 349 participants. Stratified proportionate random sampling and Slovin's formula were used to ensure fair representation across the different schools. The validated and reliable survey instrument focused on two major dimensions: the impact of the program in terms of learning and technology support, school facilities, training and development, and partnerships; and its relevance to school operations and governance, including infrastructure, quality of teaching, stakeholder engagement, resource mobilization, and accountability. Findings revealed that prior to implementation, the ASP's presence was minimally felt across most key areas. However, significant improvements were observed post-implementation, particularly in enhancing physical infrastructure and technology. Respondents reported that the program contributed to the development of resource-abundant, learner-friendly environments and fostered deeper collaboration among stakeholders. Moreover, the ASP was found to be highly aligned with schools' priorities, especially in addressing infrastructure gaps and promoting community engagement. Key policy recommendations include strengthening partnerships with the private sector, institutionalizing transparent mechanisms for resource allocation, and tailoring support to the distinct needs of each school. Ultimately, this study affirms the ASP's value as a strategic intervention to improve public education and proposes actionable pathways to enhance its long-term effectiveness.

Keywords: Adopt-a-School Program, Impact, Relevance

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INTRODUCTION

The school and the government likely need external assistance to provide a direct solution. (Stuart, 2024). According to DepEd Order no. 2, s. (2013), it is essential to revisit and strengthen Republic Act 8525 to build and sustain a mutual connection between DepEd and partners by providing a venue for the strong and dynamic private sector to participate in nation-building through investments in the education of Filipino children.

Without external aid, the school and government may struggle to provide a direct remedy. Thus, partnership and involvement in schools through community engagement are critical for actively participating in enhancing and sustaining the quality of public education. As a result, community involvement encourages teamwork, with the school, families, and community working together to create networks of shared responsibility for student success and overall school improvement. These are the reasons the researcher is interested in examining the impact of the adopt-a-school program in public schools, and the findings may inform a school-based policy program.

However, the public schools in the Philippines are still characterized by alarming issues such as the shortage of classrooms and learning materials, insufficient health services for the students, high student-teacher ratio, insufficient educator training, and the low salary of teachers. These dilemmas directly affect the quality of education, which made our country academically lag behind when compared to the neighboring nations in Asia. A number of programs were already made to remedy these situations, but problems with the implementation are the main reasons that encumber the eradication thereof (Dumpit, 2021).

Without external aid, the school and government may not be able to give a direct remedy. Thus, partnership and involvement in schools through community engagement are critical for actively participating in enhancing and sustaining the quality of public education. As a result, community involvement encourages teamwork in which the school, families, and community work together to create networks of shared responsibility for student success and overall school improvement. These are the reasons why the researcher is interested in looking at the impact of the adopt-a-school program in public schools, and the findings may be used to suggest a school-based policy program.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to determine the impact and relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program among public schools within one district of the Division of Negros Occidental for the school year 2025–2026. It sought to provide insights that could serve as a basis for school-based policy formulation. Specifically, the study explored the impact of the program on public schools from 2020 to 2024 across several key areas, including the provision of learning technology supports, the enhancement of school facilities, the implementation of training and development initiatives, and the establishment of meaningful partnerships.

Furthermore, the study examined the relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program to the overall operation and governance of public schools. This included its influence on infrastructure and the learning environment, the quality of teaching and learning, the engagement of community members and stakeholders, the mobilization of resources and promotion of innovation, and the enhancement of governance and accountability within schools.

The study also sought to identify the specific ways in which the Adopt-a-School Program has affected public schools and the extent to which the program aligns with the objectives and priorities of individual schools. Finally, the research aimed to generate policy recommendations that could guide the effective implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program, ensuring that it continues to support the development and improvement of public schools in the district.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adopt-a-School Program policy framework

The Department of Education (DepEd), in collaboration with the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR), grants incentives to DepEd's private partners. Incentives are provided through tax deductions (gross income) for private companies, industries, and private individuals who provide financial and/or in-kind services to public schools.

This provides opportunities for donor partners to apply for the availment of tax incentives or tax exemption arising from the partners' expenses incurred in the program since such entitlement is permitted under Republic Act No. 8525, otherwise known as the Adopt-a-School Act of 1998, and Revenue Regulations No. 10-2003.

DepEd private partners are welcome to avail the tax incentives as long as they meet the requirements. Partners can give their support packages through (a) infrastructure, physical facilities, furniture and real state (b) learning support (c) health and nutrition (d) reading program (e) technology support (f) direct assistance (g) training and development (h) assistive learning device for students with special needs (DepEd Order no.2, s. 2013).

According to the study of Sun (2019) entitled “Linking School Effectiveness and School improvement through “Adopt-a-School Program” found out that the Education regarding the program and possibilities of strengthening the school and the program itself. The findings provided a platform to adopters, SEF, government school representatives and government officials to collectively discuss program-related issues and reach a consensus regarding key policy recommendations. A significant number of recommendations and ideas emerged from the range of stakeholders. During the preliminary round, adopters of all the Adopt-A-School Program schools were invited to reflect on the findings of the situation analysis conducted by SEF and to develop a concrete work plan for the course of activities of the program for the coming years. The focused of the organized ADS was on providing a platform to facilitate dialogue between the government and adopters to explore avenues for program strengthening. It also provided an opportunity to reflect on existing roles and responsibilities of key program stakeholders and to collectively propose changes and recommendations regarding the program’s future course of action.

Impact on Technology and Learning and Infrastructure Development

The impact of the Adopt-a-School Program on learning and technology support has been widely documented in recent educational studies. Bell and O’Dwyer (2020) emphasized that integrating digital tools such as laptops and internet connectivity through public-private partnerships enhanced student motivation and participation, aligning with the goals of 21st-century education. Similarly, a DepEd (2017) report highlighted how ICT integration, enabled by ASP partnerships, helped bridge the digital divide in public schools and provided students with access to modern learning resources. These technological supports have played a significant role in improving classroom instruction and fostering digital literacy.

In terms of school infrastructure development, Barrett et al. (2015) confirmed that improvements in school facilities—such as classroom renovation, sanitation, and recreational spaces—have a direct influence on student attendance, academic performance, and well-being. This is supported by UNESCO (2015), which reported that infrastructure upgrades facilitated through Adopt-a-School initiatives helped create safer, more conducive learning environments. These enhancements are essential in ensuring equity for learners in underserved communities.

On the theme of teacher training and professional development, Levin (2012) argued that external support from partners in ASPs strengthens institutional capacity by equipping teachers with skills needed for improved instruction. Guskey (2002) also noted that effective teacher training initiatives lead to sustainable change in classroom practices, which ultimately benefits student learning outcomes. These studies underscore the relevance of ASPs in enhancing the quality of teaching through continuous professional development.

A lot of educational literature shows that the Adopt-a-School Program is important for improving the infrastructure and learning environment. Barrett et al. (2015) asserted that educational environments significantly influence student outcomes. The ASP has made many public schools safer and more welcoming places to learn by improving the classrooms, bathrooms, and play areas. UNESCO (2015) also said that partnerships based on the ASP model quickly fixed major problems with public school infrastructure, making it easier for students who are not in the mainstream to get an education and study.

It's clear that ASP is important for improving teaching and learning because it makes it easier to make lessons better. Bell and O’Dwyer (2020) found that ASP-sponsored programs, like giving teachers digital tools and training, improve teaching methods and make students more interested in class. Guskey (2002) said that these programs' funding for professional development helps teachers do their jobs better, which is directly linked to how well students do in school. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2018) also said that private sector involvement is important for improving training opportunities and raising the professional standards of teachers.

Community Engagement

ASP has also been very helpful in getting people in the community and other important people involved. Bray (2000) said that including stakeholders in education builds trust and a sense of shared responsibility. This is consistent with the findings of UNICEF Philippines (2019), which indicated that ASP programs facilitate collaboration among schools, local communities, and the business sector, resulting in more responsive, needs-based support for schools and students. This kind of involvement makes people more responsible and encourages them to invest in making schools better over time.

Despite their potential benefits, ASPs are often plagued by implementation challenges that can hinder their effectiveness and sustainability. Dimayuga (2022) identified challenges such as mismatched expectations between adopters and schools, lack of clear

guidelines, and inconsistent participation. These issues underscore the need for structured frameworks to ensure program sustainability.

A recurring theme in the literature is the reliance on short-term funding cycles and the lack of long-term commitment from adopting partners (Santos, 2023). This leads to project discontinuity, making it difficult to achieve sustainable improvements. Organizations like PBSP (2023) emphasize the need for multi-year funding agreements to ensure program continuity.

Another challenge in ASP implementation, according to Bautista & Tolentino (2021), is that the inconsistent participation from adopters can hinder the long-term success of ASP. Schools often face uncertainty when adopters withdraw support prematurely, leading to incomplete projects and unmet needs.

Poor communication and lack of coordination between schools, partners, and local government units are frequently cited as obstacles (Reyes, 2020). Effective communication requires establishing clear channels, regular meetings, and transparent reporting mechanisms.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method sequential explanatory design, consisting of a quantitative survey followed by qualitative thematic analysis, which involved collecting data in the field directly from the respondents who were experiencing the issue or problem being studied. This study encompasses philosophical assumptions, employs both qualitative and quantitative methodologies, and incorporates a combination and/or integration of these approaches.

The mixed-method sequential explanatory design comprises two separate phases: a quantitative phase followed by a qualitative phase (Creswell et al., 2003 as quoted by Oquindo, 2022). In this design, a researcher initially gathers and examines the quantitative (numeric) data. The qualitative data is gathered and examined as the second step in the process, providing further insight and clarification on the quantitative findings gained in the initial phase. The second phase, which is qualitative, builds upon the previous phase, which is quantitative. These two phases are connected during the intermediate portion of the study.

Moreover, the research methodology was suitable for this study as it sought to gather data pertaining to the impact and relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program among public schools during the academic year 2024-2025. The survey questionnaire was utilized to evaluate the impact and relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program among public schools. Conversely, open-ended questions were employed to gather qualitative data. The survey questionnaire and assessment of pertinent literature formed the foundation for the open-ended questions. The study utilized questions and recurring themes to examine the responses provided by the participants.

Phase I: Quantitative

Respondents of the Study

This section of the research focuses on key respondents essential to the study's success. The teachers, school leaders and PTA members of public schools in the district of Manapla, Division of Negros Occidental, are directly involved in the school's adopt-a-school program. The research's respondents comprise three categories: selected teachers, school leaders and PTA members. The selection will be carried out using stratified proportionate random sampling, categorizing respondents by schools. The respondents consisted of 207 teachers, 14 school leaders, and 128 PTA officers, for a total of 349 participants. In determining the respondents for this study, stratified proportionate random sampling was used. Their experiences and perspectives are crucial to understanding the program's impact and relevance and areas for improvement. The researcher respected respondents' time and willingness to join, obtaining informed consent and ensuring they can withdraw without consequence. Ethical standards, including confidentiality and anonymity, will be strictly maintained to protect participants' privacy and sensitive information.

The total population of the three types of respondents was summed up to obtain the sample size and Slovin's formula was used. To determine the number of respondents per category, the researcher computed the percentage by dividing the total population of each program to the total number of the two programs then multiply to the sample size and proportionately distributed to the number of respondents.

Sampling Procedure

Gay (2012) defines stratified proportionate random sampling as a method of selecting a sample in which every individual in the specified population has an equal and independent probability of selection. The sample sizes inside each stratum are determined proportionally to the sizes of the strata when the overall sample size is fixed at n . Each school may offer distinct insights into the effects of its adopt-a-school program. Due to the impracticality of surveying the entire population, a comprehensive sampling technique will be employed to select a representative sample, encompassing a varied array of participants to get insights pertinent to various sectors within the Manapla district. Systematic or stratified sampling approaches were employed to guarantee an accurate representation of the population.

The respondents completed both qualitative and quantitative questionnaires to assess impact and relevance of the Adopt-a-School Program among public schools.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents

Schools	School Leaders		Teachers		PTA	
	N	%	N	%	n	%
VICMICO	1	6	13	6	4	2
PUNTA SALONG	1	6	12	6	13	7
Don Cornelio	1	6	7	3	13	7
Sta Teresa ES	1	6	5	2	11	6
Gregorio Montinola ES	1	6	7	3	6	3
Don Emilio Miraflores Sr. Memorial Es	1	6	8	4	10	5
Patlagan ES	1	6	4	2	9	5
SAARBA ES	1	6	4	2	13	7
Chambery ES	1	6	9	4	12	6
Punta Mesa ES	1	6	9	4	16	9
Tortosa IS	1	6	10	5	9	5
Mesde	1	6	5	3	7	4
Lauron	1	6	4	2	12	6
Begonia	1	6	5	3	11	6
Manapla	1	6	29	14	9	5
Manapla NHS	1	6	60	29	7	4
Purisima	1	6	11	5	15	8

Quinaroyan	1	6	6	3	11	6
Total	14	100	207	100	128	100

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a survey, administered a researcher-made questionnaire to the study's respondents, in accordance with the provisions of Republic Act 8525. The parameters of the survey instrument were anchored on the areas in DepEd Order No. 66, series of 2003.

The researchers used a validated and reliable instrument to collect the necessary data. The data-gathering instrument administered to the respondents was composed of two (2) major parts. Part I is the respondent's identification information, which required them to supply or check the needed information concerning their position in the school organization. Part II of the instrument was the questionnaire proper, consisting of 25 items with 4 areas of concern, namely learning and technology supports, physical facilities, training and development, and partnerships, to determine the impact of the adopt-a-school program on the public school as assessed by school leaders, teachers, and PTA members. The items were answerable on a 5-point scale: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Neither Agree nor Disagree), 2 (Disagree), and 1 (Strongly Disagree). The corresponding numerical value is converted into scales below.

To determine the relevance of the adopt-a-school program in the public school as perceived by school leaders, teachers, and PTA members, the instrument is the questionnaire proper, consisting of 25 items with 5 areas of concern, namely infrastructure and learning environment, quality of teaching and learning, community and stakeholder engagement, resource mobilization and innovation, and enhancing governance and accountability. The items were answerable on a 5-point scale: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Neither agree nor Disagree), 2 (Disagree), and 1 (Strongly Disagree). The corresponding numerical value is converted into scales below.

Rating	Range	Descriptors	Interpretation
1	1.00 - 1.49	Strongly Disagree	No impact
2	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Minimal impact
3	2.50 - 3.49	Neither agree nor Disagree	Moderate impact
4	3.50 - 4.49	Agree	Significant impact
5	4.50 - 5.00	Strongly agree	Very significant impact

To determine the relevance of adopt-a-school program of among the public school as perceived by school leaders, teacher and PTA members, instrument is the questionnaire proper consisting of 25 items with 5 areas of concerns namely: infrastructure and learning environment, quality of teaching and learning, community and stakeholder engagement, resource mobilization and innovation, and enhancing governance and accountability. The items were answerable of a 5 point scale: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Neither agree nor Disagree), 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strong Disagree). The corresponding numerical value is converted into scales below.

Rating	Range	Descriptors	Interpretation
1	1.00 - 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Relevant
2	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Relevant

3	2.50 - 3.49	Neither agree nor Disagree	Moderately Relevant
4	3.50 - 4.49	Agree	Relevant
5	4.50 - 5.00	Strongly agree	Highly Relevant

Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to validation by 9 professional evaluators in the field, employing the commonly used assessment of content validity, the item content ratio (CVR), as established by Waltz and Bausell in 1981 and by Lyn in 1986. The validators will evaluate the questionnaire content item by item and assign ratings according to the established relevance scale. The Lawshe Content Validity Tool was used to validate both the survey and interview questionnaires. Nine experts will examine and rate whether each item in the questionnaire is essential, essential but not necessary, or not essential. All survey and interview questionnaire questions that yielded a CVR of .97 or higher were considered valid and able to answer the research questions.

Reliability of the Instrument

An instrument is said to be reliable when it has the capacity to yield stable, consistent data needed for this investigation. To meet this requirement, the researcher conducted a dry run of the instrument with 30 individuals from the other district who were not part of the final set of respondents. The data gathered were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha. The study instrument's dependability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. The quantitative reliability measure was established through a reliability test conducted in another school division. Using Cronbach's Alpha, the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire items (.87) is highly reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the office of the superintendent and the public school supervisor to conduct the survey and administer the questionnaire to the selected school leaders, teachers, and PTA officers.

After permission was approved, the researcher used an electronic survey form to gather data on the relevance and impact of the adopt-a-school program. The respondents were informed of the study's objectives and assured of the confidentiality of their responses. The instruments' responses were gathered, encoded, tallied, and interpreted in accordance with the conceptual design and the specific objectives of the study.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data analysis for this study involved several key steps. First, the respondents' data were organized to ensure accuracy and reliability. A descriptive analysis was used to examine the respondents' responses, using statistics such as means, percentages, and frequencies. Quantitative methods, including the mean, were used to explore the program's effects in the areas. These findings were integrated to provide a comprehensive view of the program's relevance and impact. Finally, the results were interpreted in light of the research objectives, and their implications were discussed. The study also acknowledged limitations and offered recommendations for future research and data improvements. For the problem concerning the impact of adopt-a-school among public schools from 2020 to 2024 based on learning and technology supports, school facilities, training and development, and partnerships, the mean and standard deviation were used.

For the problem concerning the relevance of the adopt-a-school program to the public schools' operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment, quality of teaching and learning, community and stakeholder engagement, resource mobilization and innovation, and enhanced governance and accountability, means and standard deviations were used.

Phase II: Qualitative

Participants of the Study

The qualitative phase of the study involved ten (10) participants drawn from ten (10) different public schools. The participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: (1) they must be currently and permanently employed public school teachers; (2) they must have at least five (5) years of teaching experience; and (3) they must be willing to participate in the study.

A convenience sampling technique was employed to select participants who were considered “information-rich” and capable of providing meaningful insights relevant to the research objectives. The selection process carefully considered participants’ availability, accessibility, preferences, and willingness to engage in the study. This approach ensured that the participants possessed sufficient professional experience and contextual understanding of the Adopt-a-School Program.

Research Instrument

The qualitative data were gathered using an open-ended questionnaire designed specifically for teachers. The instrument focused on eliciting in-depth responses regarding their experiences and perceptions of the Adopt-a-School Program.

The qualitative section of the questionnaire included the following key questions:

In what ways has the Adopt-a-School Program impacted public schools?

To what extent and in what manner does the Adopt-a-School Program align with your school's objectives and priorities?

These open-ended questions allowed participants to freely express their perspectives, thereby generating rich descriptive data essential for understanding the program’s implementation and outcomes.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the respective school heads to conduct the study. The identified participants were informed about the purpose of the research, and their voluntary participation was emphasized. Informed consent was obtained before the administration of the questionnaire.

The qualitative questionnaires were distributed personally and/or electronically, depending on participants’ accessibility and preference. Participants were given sufficient time to respond to ensure thoughtful and comprehensive answers. Completed questionnaires were collected and compiled for analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure

The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, guided by the six-step phenomenological procedure outlined by Creswell (1998, 2014). This approach was employed specifically to address Research Problems 3 and 4, which examine (1) the ways the Adopt-a-School Program has impacted public schools and (2) the extent to which the program aligns with the schools’ objectives and priorities.

The analysis began with data organization and preparation. All gathered responses were compiled and transcribed. Where applicable, audio-recorded interviews were carefully reviewed and transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy. The researcher repeatedly read the transcripts to achieve immersion and gain a comprehensive understanding of the participants’ lived experiences.

During the initial reading, significant statements relevant to the research questions were identified. Marginal notes were written to record preliminary insights and general impressions. The process of coding followed, wherein meaningful units of data were bracketed and assigned category labels, often reflecting the participants’ own language.

Subsequently, related codes were grouped into clusters to form categories. These categories were further synthesized into broader themes that captured the central patterns emerging from the data. The researcher refined and consolidated these themes into a manageable number (typically five to seven major themes) to ensure clarity and coherence.

The final phase involved developing rich textual descriptions of each theme and integrating them into a qualitative narrative. The findings were presented through a thematic discussion highlighting key insights, patterns, and lessons learned regarding the impact and alignment of the Adopt-a-School Program. Interpretation of the results focused on capturing the essential meanings of

participants' experiences, consistent with Lincoln and Guba's (1985, as cited in Creswell, 2014) emphasis on drawing meaningful lessons from qualitative inquiry.

Data Trustworthiness

To ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative findings, the study adhered to the principles of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility was strengthened by selecting experienced teachers who were directly involved in school operations and familiar with the Adopt-a-School Program. Transferability was addressed by providing a clear description of the participants and research context. Dependability was ensured through a systematic and well-documented data collection and analysis process. Confirmability was maintained by grounding interpretations in participants' actual responses and minimizing researcher bias. These measures enhanced the rigor and integrity of the qualitative phase of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were carefully integrated into both qualitative and quantitative phases of this study to safeguard participant rights and reduce potential harm. Before any data is collected, participants must be fully informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights to give informed consent, which is the cornerstone of this approach. Given that the study respondents included school leaders, teachers, and PTA members, ethical considerations, including confidentiality, anonymity, and the avoidance of deceit, were taken into account throughout the development of the research instrument. Furthermore, a brief orientation will be done for the study participants to alleviate any apprehension. The data collected throughout the study addressed confidentiality, as Part 1 of the research instrument allowed respondents to provide their identities and other personal information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2

The Impact of Adopt-a-School Program Among the Public Schools Based on Learning and Technology Supports

Learning And Technology Supports	Before		After		Remark
	M	I	M	I	
A School Program has/been					
1. provided support and donations have enabled a significant increase in regular attendance among learners, providing targeted resources that address barriers like health, fees, and engagement.	2.07	Minimal Impact	4.06	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact
2. ensured that learners from the most disadvantaged backgrounds receive prioritized access to scholarships, meals, supplies, and counseling, resulting in more equitable educational outcomes across our partner schools.	1.87	Minimal Impact	4.01	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact
3. provided support and donations have enabled a significant increase in regular attendance, targeting the underlying barriers faced by underprivileged learners, including health, financial strain, and access to education resources.	1.85	Minimal Impact	4.01	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact
increased availability of instructional materials, such as textbooks and modules, has significantly enhanced students' learning experiences, leading to improved academic performance and greater engagement in the learning process.	1.86	Minimal Impact	4.22	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact
5. availability of more effective instructional tools—such as interactive digital platforms, multimedia resources, and hands-on materials—has significantly enhanced student learning by accommodating diverse learning styles, fostering engagement, and improving academic performance.	2.70	Minimal Impact	4.20	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact

6. the availability of instructional materials such as textbooks and modules has significantly improved, leading to enhanced student learning outcomes. This initiative has provided students with the necessary resources to develop foundational skills in reading and mathematics, fostering a more effective and inclusive learning environment.

3.26	Minimal Impact	4.21	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact	
Overall Mean	2.26	Minimal Impact	4.11	Significant impact	Positive and significant increase in impact

The data in Table 2 shows a positive and significant increase in impact on the adopt-a-school program among public schools before and after they underwent the program on learning and technology supports.

The mean score of 2.26 for the adopt-a-school program among public schools before the implementation of learning and technology support. The highest mean score, 3.26, comes from Item 6. The accessibility of instructional materials, including textbooks and modules, has markedly improved, resulting in better student learning results. This project has equipped students with essential materials to develop fundamental skills in reading and mathematics, promoting a more efficient and equitable educational environment.

The lowest mean score, 1.85, is observed for Item 3: The accessibility of instructional materials, including textbooks and modules, has markedly improved, resulting in better student learning outcomes. This project has equipped students with essential materials to develop fundamental skills in reading and mathematics, promoting a more efficient and equitable educational environment.

Moreover, Table 2 also illustrates a significant impact among the three respondents on the adopt-a-school program in public schools after its implementation on learning and technology supports. According to the assessment, the overall mean score of 4.11 was interpreted as indicating a "significant impact" of the adopt-a-school program on public schools based on learning and technology supports. Item 4 yields the highest mean score of 4.22, indicating a "significant impact." The augmented availability of instructional materials, including textbooks and modules, has markedly improved students' learning experiences, resulting in enhanced academic achievement and heightened involvement in the educational process.

The lowest mean score of 4.01 (indicating significant impact) is observed for Items 2 and 3. The school guaranteed that learners from the most disadvantaged backgrounds received prioritized access to scholarships, food, supplies, and counselling, leading to more equal educational outcomes throughout our partner schools.

This large rise implies that measures such as donation support, access to teaching materials, and the deployment of digital tools have had a direct impact on tackling crucial educational barriers. These include concerns about student health, budgetary restraints, involvement, and a lack of learning tools.

Notably, the program has been successful in increasing regular attendance, particularly among students from underprivileged backgrounds, by providing critical support such as scholarships, school meals, and counselling. This tailored strategy has resulted in more equitable learning environments and increased academic performance throughout the partner schools.

Furthermore, the greater availability of instructional and technical materials has enhanced the learning experience while also accommodating varied learning styles, making the learning environment more inclusive and engaging. Students now have access to resources that help them develop both foundational and advanced skills, particularly in literacy and numeracy.

In general, the results show that the Adopt-a-School Program is a highly effective educational intervention. It has made a significant contribution to improving educational access and quality, demonstrating good replication and scalability in other impoverished school communities. The steady increase in all measures demonstrates the program's relevance, responsiveness, and sustainability as a model for tackling educational inequality.

Tan, A. (2018), community and private-sector engagement led to significant improvements in technology availability in public schools. Focuses on the role of technology in improving classroom outcomes, indirectly citing the impact of government

programs, including Adopt-a-School. Offers comparative data that supports the idea that technology-enhanced learning environments, like those facilitated through Adopt-a-School, yield better academic results.

Table 3

The Relevance of Adopt-a-School Program To The Public Schools' Operation And Governance In Terms Of Infrastructure And Learning Environment

INFRASTRUCTURE AND LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	Teachers		School Head		PTA Officers	
	M	I	M	I	M	I
1. Some improvements have been made to the classrooms' physical condition, including repairs, painting, and roofing.	4.19	Relevant	4.50	Highly Relevant	4.32	Relevant
2. There has been an increase in the availability of facilities such as libraries, labs, and canteens.	3.91	Relevant	3.71	Relevant	4.03	Relevant
3. There have been enhancements made to the school grounds, such as playgrounds and gardens, and they have been better maintained.	4.06	Relevant	4.50	Highly Relevant	4.15	Relevant
4. These enhancements have resulted in an increase in the pupils' positive behavior as well as their discipline.	4.06	Relevant	4.57	Highly Relevant	4.15	Relevant
5. The environment of the school as a whole has evolved to reflect a more favorable environment for learning.	4.17	Relevant	4.57	Highly Relevant	4.18	Relevant
Overall Mean	4.07	Relevant	4.37	Relevant	4.16	Relevant

Table 3 illustrates the relevance of adopt-a-school program to the public schools' operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment, the results revealed that among the three respondents on the adopt-a-school program in public schools operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment, with means of 4.07 for teachers, 4.37 for school heads and 4.37 for PTA officers which interpreted as "Relevant".

According to the assessment provided by teachers, the overall mean score of 4.07 was interpreted as indicating a "Relevant" of the adopt-a-school program on public schools' operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment. Item 1 yields the highest mean score of 4.19, indicating a "relevant", Improvements have been made to the classrooms' physical condition, including repairs, painting, and roofing. The lowest mean score of 3.91 (relevant) is observed in Item 2, there has been an increase in the availability of facilities such as libraries, labs, and canteens.

Furthermore, the mean score of 4.37 from school heads indicates the "relevant" of the adopt-a-school program on public schools' operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment, as assessed by the school heads. Items 4 and 5 yield the highest mean score of 4.57, the environment of the school as a whole has evolved to reflect a more favorable environment for learning. The lowest mean score of 3.71 is observed in Item 2, there has been an increase in the availability of facilities such as libraries, labs, and canteens. Furthermore, the overall mean score of 4.16 indicates "relevant" of the adopt-a-school initiative on public schools' operation and governance in terms of infrastructure and learning environment, as evaluated

by PTA officers. Item 1 yields the highest mean score of 4.32, interpreted as "relevant". Improvements have been made to the classrooms' physical condition, including repairs, painting, and roofing. Item 2 exhibits the lowest mean score of 4.03, there has been an increase in the availability of facilities such as libraries, labs, and canteens.

The results imply that the program plays an important role in supporting school operations by contributing to improved infrastructure and creating a more conducive learning environment. The consistent high ratings across all groups emphasize that the program is aligned with the needs of public schools and is seen as a valuable mechanism for enhancing both educational facilities and governance structures. The higher ratings from school heads and PTA officers may reflect their broader perspective on school management and community involvement in maintaining school infrastructure and ensuring quality education.

This pattern corresponds with Bautista's (2015) findings, which indicated that although enhancements to school infrastructure through public-private partnerships frequently prioritize immediate classroom need, assistance for ancillary facilities remains variable. UNICEF (2019) underscored that comprehensive learning environments encompass not just well-maintained classrooms but also accessible educational resources, like libraries and laboratories, which are essential for 21st-century education.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study revealed that the Adopt-a-School Program has significantly contributed to the improvement of public-school operations and learning environments. Prior to the implementation of the program, teachers, school heads, and PTA officers perceived minimal impact in areas such as learning and technology support, school facilities, training and development, and stakeholder collaboration. The relatively low mean scores indicated limited engagement and insufficient resources in these critical areas. However, after the program's implementation, the results showed a notable increase in mean scores across all dimensions, particularly in school facilities and learning and technology support. These improvements demonstrate that the program effectively enhanced physical infrastructure, digital resources, and instructional tools, strengthening both school management and teaching practices.

Furthermore, the findings confirm that the Adopt-a-School Program is highly relevant to the governance and operations of public schools. High mean ratings across key domains including infrastructure development, teaching quality, stakeholder engagement, resource mobilization, and transparency in management indicate that the program plays an important role in strengthening school systems. The program fostered a learner-centered environment by improving classrooms, upgrading technology and facilities, and promoting educational collaboration among schools, private partners, and community stakeholders. These outcomes highlight how the program supports the advancement of quality education and encourages shared responsibility in school development.

The study also emphasizes the broader significance of the program in addressing students' needs and supporting holistic school development. By mobilizing support from private sector partners and community stakeholders, schools were able to enhance learning environments, improve facilities, and access additional educational resources. The strengthened collaboration contributed to improved instructional practices and helped schools respond more effectively to the academic and well-being needs of learners. These results demonstrate that the program aligns strongly with the goals and priorities of public education. Despite these positive findings, the study acknowledges certain limitations that may affect the generalizability of the results, such as the focus on a specific district and reliance on respondents' perceptions. Nevertheless, the overall evidence suggests that the Adopt-a-School Program remains a valuable strategy for improving school infrastructure, strengthening partnerships, and enhancing educational outcomes. The study therefore highlights the importance of sustaining and further strengthening the program to ensure continuous support for public schools and to promote long-term educational development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Adopt-a-School Program should continue strengthening partnerships with private sector organizations, community groups, and other stakeholders to ensure sustained support for public schools. Strong collaboration can help mobilize additional resources needed for improving learning environments, instructional materials, and school operations. Encouraging active participation among teachers, school heads, and PTA officers will also foster a stronger sense of shared responsibility and ownership in implementing school improvement initiatives.
2. The program should expand its support for school infrastructure and technology to maintain the significant progress already achieved. Continuous investment in digital resources, teaching tools, and modern facilities will help schools create more learner-

centered environments that respond to the needs of 21st-century education. Improving access to updated technology and well-maintained infrastructure can further enhance the quality of teaching and learning.

3. A continuous professional development programs for teachers and school leaders should be prioritized. Providing regular training opportunities can strengthen instructional practices, leadership skills, and collaboration among educators. These initiatives will ensure that teachers and school administrators remain equipped with the knowledge and competencies necessary to effectively manage resources, adopt innovative teaching approaches, and support students' academic development.

4. Establishing clear and transparent monitoring and evaluation mechanisms is essential to sustain the effectiveness of the Adopt-a-School Program. Regular assessment of program implementation will help ensure accountability, measure outcomes, and identify areas for improvement. Strengthening these systems will enable schools and partners to maintain the program's positive impact and ensure its long-term contribution to the development of public education.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. There were no financial, personal, or institutional relationships that could have inappropriately influenced or biased the results and interpretations of the research. The study was conducted independently and objectively, in accordance with ethical research standards.

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